

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

**BULLETIN OF FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

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КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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Адрес редакции:

Республика Узбекистан, 200100, г.
Бухара, ул. Гиждуванская, 23.

Телефон (99865) 223-00-50

Факс (99866) 223-00-50

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e-mail baymuradovravshan@gmail.com

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CLINICAL AND FUNCTIONAL OUTCOMES OF A COMPREHENSIVE EARLY REHABILITATION PROGRAMME AFTER ANKLE JOINT SURGERY

Usmonov O.A., Rizaev J.A.

Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

Resume. Background. Standard postoperative rehabilitation after ankle surgery in lower-resource settings is often empirical, leading to suboptimal functional outcomes. The aim of this study was to evaluate clinical and functional outcomes of a comprehensive multimodal early rehabilitation programme based on Fast-track principles. Methods. Prospective controlled non-randomised study of 132 patients after ankle surgery: main group (n = 73, 2023–2025) — comprehensive programme; control group (n = 59, 2020–2022) — standard rehabilitation. Outcomes were assessed using AOFAS, OMAS, FAOS scales, goniometry, podometry and stabilometry at weeks 2, 4 and 6. Results. At week 6, the AOFAS score reached 86.4 ± 8.1 in the main group vs 71.2 ± 10.3 in the control ($p < 0.001$), corresponding to "good" category in 52.1 % vs 13.6 % of patients. OMAS score: 84.5 ± 8.5 vs 70.2 ± 10.5 ($p < 0.001$). FAOS Quality of Life subscale: 71.8 vs 52.6 ($p < 0.001$). Biomechanical recovery (% of age-specific reference): podometry 89–94 % vs 77–85 %; stabilometry 84–89 % vs 56–64 % ($p < 0.001$ for all parameters). Functional Recovery Index ≥ 90 %: 52.1 % vs 13.6 % ($p < 0.001$). Conclusions. The comprehensive early rehabilitation programme demonstrated statistically and clinically significant improvements in functional outcomes compared with standard rehabilitation, with results comparable to or exceeding those reported in international Fast-track studies.

Keywords: ankle surgery, early rehabilitation, AOFAS, OMAS, FAOS, podometry, stabilometry, Fast-track, multimodal programme.

БОЛДИР - ТЎПИҚ БЎҒИМИ ОПЕРАЦИЯСИДАН КЕЙИНГИ КОМПЛЕКС ЭРТА РЕАБИЛИТАЦИЯ ДАСТУРИНИНГ КЛИНИК ВА ФУНКЦИОНАЛ НАТИЖАЛАРИ

Усмонов О.А., Ризаев Ж.А.

Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети, Самарқанд ш., Ўзбекистон

Резюме. Кириш. Чекланган ресурслар шароитида болдир - тўпиқ бўғимидаги операциялардан кейинги стандарт операциядан кейинги реабилитация кўпинча эмпирик хусусиятга эга бўлиб, бу қониқарсиз функционал натижаларга олиб келади. Ушбу тадқиқотнинг мақсади тезлаштирилган реабилитация тамойилларига асосланган комплекс мултимодал эрта реабилитация дастурининг клиник ва функционал натижаларини баҳолашдан иборат эди. (Fast-track). Усуллар. болдир - тўпиқ бўғимида ўтказилган жарроҳлик амалиётидан сўнг 132 нафар беморни проспектив назорат қилинадиган рандомизатсияланмаган тадқиқоти: асосий гуруҳ (n = 73, 2023-2025 йиллар) - комплекс дастур; назорат гуруҳи (n = 59, 2020-2022 йиллар) - стандарт реабилитация. Натижалар AOFAS, OMAS, FAOS, гониометрия, подометрия ва стабилметрия шкаллари ёрдамида 2, 4 ва 6 ҳафталазда баҳоланди. Натижалар. 6-ҳафтада AOFAS шкаласи бўйича баҳолаш асосий гуруҳда $86,4 \pm 8,1$ га, назорат гуруҳида эса $71,2 \pm 10,3$ га етди ($p < 0,001$), бу беморларнинг 52,1 фоизиди 13,6 фоизга нисбатан "яхши ҳолат" тоифасига тўғри келади. OMAS шкаласи бўйича баҳолаш: $84,5 \pm 8,5$ га қарши $70,2 \pm 10,5$ ($p < 0,001$). FAOS ҳаёт сифати кичик шкаласи: 52,6 га қарши 71,8 ($p < 0,001$). Биомеханик тикланиш (ёшга боғлиқ кўрсаткичларга нисбатан %): подометрия 89-94% га қарши 77-85%; стабилметрия 84-89% га қарши 56-64% (барча кўрсаткичлар учун $p < 0,001$). Функционал тикланиш индекси $\geq 90\%$: 52,1% га қарши 13,6% ($p < 0,001$). Хулосалар. Эрта реабилитациянинг кенг қамровли дастури стандарт реабилитацияга нисбатан функционал натижаларнинг статистик ва клиник жиҳатдан сезиларли яхшиланишини кўрсатди, унинг натижалари халқаро Fast-track тадқиқотларида олинган натижалар билан таққосланади ёки улардан устун туради.

Калит сўзлар: болдир – тўпиқ бўғими хирургияси, эрта реабилитация, AOFAS, OMAS, FAOS, подометрия, стабилметрия, Fast-track, мултимодал дастур.

КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ И ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ КОМПЛЕКСНОЙ ПРОГРАММЫ РАННЕЙ РЕАБИЛИТАЦИИ ПОСЛЕ ОПЕРАЦИИ НА ГОЛЕНОСТОПНОМ СУСТАВЕ

Усмонов О.А., Ризаев Ж.А.

Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет, г. Самарканд, Узбекистан

Резюме. Введение. Стандартная послеоперационная реабилитация после операций на голено-

стопном суставе в условиях ограниченных ресурсов часто носит эмпирический характер, что приводит к неудовлетворительным функциональным результатам. Целью данного исследования была оценка клинических и функциональных результатов комплексной мультимодальной программы ранней реабилитации, основанной на принципах ускоренной реабилитации (Fast-track). Методы. Проспективное контролируемое нерандомизированное исследование 132 пациентов после операций на голеностопном суставе: основная группа ($n = 73$, 2023–2025 гг.) — комплексная программа; контрольная группа ($n = 59$, 2020–2022 гг.) — стандартная реабилитация. Результаты оценивались с использованием шкал AOFAS, OMAS, FAOS, гониометрии, подометрии и стабиллометрии на 2, 4 и 6 неделях. Результаты. На 6-й неделе оценка по шкале AOFAS достигла $86,4 \pm 8,1$ в основной группе против $71,2 \pm 10,3$ в контрольной группе ($p < 0,001$), что соответствует категории «хорошее состояние» у 52,1 % против 13,6 % пациентов. Оценка по шкале OMAS: $84,5 \pm 8,5$ против $70,2 \pm 10,5$ ($p < 0,001$). Подшкала качества жизни FAOS: 71,8 против 52,6 ($p < 0,001$). Биомеханическое восстановление (% от возрастных референтных значений): подометрия 89–94 % против 77–85 %; стабиллометрия 84–89 % против 56–64 % ($p < 0,001$ для всех параметров). Индекс функционального восстановления ≥ 90 %: 52,1 % против 13,6 % ($p < 0,001$). Выводы. Комплексная программа ранней реабилитации продемонстрировала статистически и клинически значимые улучшения функциональных результатов по сравнению со стандартной реабилитацией, результаты которой сопоставимы или превосходят результаты, полученные в международных исследованиях Fast-track.

Ключевые слова: хирургия голеностопного сустава, ранняя реабилитация, AOFAS, OMAS, FAOS, подометрия, стабиллометрия, Fast-track, мультимодальная программа.

Introduction. Ankle joint surgery encompasses a wide spectrum of procedures, from open reduction and internal fixation (ORIF) of malleolar fractures to ligament reconstruction, arthrodesis and total ankle replacement [1, 2]. Despite continuous improvements in surgical techniques, postoperative rehabilitation remains a critical determinant of long-term functional recovery. In high-income countries, structured Enhanced Recovery After Surgery (ERAS) and Fast-track protocols have demonstrated substantial improvements in functional outcomes, hospital length of stay reduction, and decreased complication rates [3, 4].

In contrast, in low- and middle-income countries postoperative rehabilitation often remains empirical and consists of prolonged immobilisation, delayed weight-bearing, and limited use of biomechanical assessment tools. This approach has been associated with persistently suboptimal functional outcomes, with mean AOFAS scores in published series rarely exceeding 75 points at 6 weeks postoperatively [5, 6]. Furthermore, psychological aspects of recovery — particularly kinesiophobia and post-traumatic anxiety — are rarely addressed despite their well-documented impact on functional outcomes [7].

The aim of this study was to evaluate clinical and functional outcomes of a comprehensive multimodal early rehabilitation programme based on Fast-track principles, applied in a single Central Asian rehabilitation centre, and to compare these outcomes with those obtained using the standard regional rehabilitation approach.

Materials and methods. Study design. A prospective controlled non-randomised single-centre study with historical control. Setting: Scientific and Practical Rehabilitation Centre at Samarkand State Medical University, Republic of Uzbekistan. Period: 2020–2025.

Participants. A total of 132 consecutive patients after ankle surgery were enrolled: ORIF of malleolar fractures ($n = 78$), ankle arthroscopy ($n = 28$), ligament reconstruction ($n = 17$), arthrodesis ($n = 6$), and total ankle replacement ($n = 3$). Age range: 18–72 years (mean 46.0 ± 14.5 years); sex: 76 males (57.6 %), 56 females (42.4 %).

Inclusion criteria: age 18–72 years; planned or emergency ankle surgery with stable fixation confirmed intraoperatively; signed informed consent. Exclusion criteria: unstable fixation, decompensated comorbidity, history of deep vein thrombosis < 3 months, psychiatric instability, refusal to participate.

Comparison groups. Main group ($n = 73$, treated 2023–2025) received the comprehensive multimodal programme based on Fast-track principles, including: (1) early activation 6–12 hours post-surgery, (2) multimodal analgesia (NSAIDs + paracetamol + local anaesthetics), (3) edema control via cryocompression and pneumocompression, (4) psychological screening with TSK-17 and HADS, (5) apparatus-based therapy (CPM, neuromuscular electrostimulation, magnetotherapy, biofeedback stabilometry from week 2). Control group ($n = 59$, treated 2020–2022) received standard regional rehabilitation: activation at 48–72 hours, opioid analgesia, plaster immobilisation 4–6 weeks, no apparatus therapy, no formal psychological screening.

Outcome measures. Functional outcomes were assessed using validated scales: AOFAS Ankle-Hindfoot Scale (0–100, "good" ≥ 85), OMAS (Olerud-Molander, 0–100), and FAOS (Foot and Ankle Outcome Score, 5 subscales). Biomechanical assessment included podometry (step length, frequency, walking

speed, load symmetry) and stabilometry (statokinesigram length with eyes open and closed, area, Romberg coefficient). All biomechanical parameters were normalised to age-specific reference values obtained from a separate cohort of 30 healthy volunteers stratified into four age groups. Functional Recovery Index (FRI) was calculated as the integral score combining all clinical and biomechanical parameters with patient stratified into four categories: Good ($\geq 90\%$), Satisfactory (70–90%), Moderate deficit (50–70%), Marked deficit ($< 50\%$). Assessments were performed at weeks 1, 2, 4 and 6 postoperatively.

Statistical analysis. Quantitative data are presented as mean \pm SD; categorical data as n (%). Between-group comparisons used Student's t-test or Mann–Whitney U-test depending on data distribution; categorical comparisons used χ^2 or Fisher exact test. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. Analysis was performed in IBM SPSS Statistics v.26.0.

Results. Demographics. The two groups did not differ significantly in age (45.5 ± 14.0 vs 46.4 ± 15.0 years), sex distribution (M:F 33:26 vs 43:30), surgery type distribution, AO/Weber classification of malleolar fractures, or comorbidity profile (all $p > 0.05$).

AOFAS and OMAS dynamics. Functional recovery on AOFAS and OMAS scales was significantly faster and reached higher final values in the main group (Figure 1). At week 6, AOFAS in the main group was 86.4 ± 8.1 vs 71.2 ± 10.3 in the control group ($p < 0.001$), with 52.1% of main-group patients reaching the "good" category (≥ 85 points) vs 13.6% in the control. OMAS at week 6: 84.5 ± 8.5 vs 70.2 ± 10.5 ($p < 0.001$).

Figure 1. Dynamics of clinical outcomes — AOFAS Ankle-Hindfoot Scale and Olerud-Molander Score

FAOS subscale analysis. The Foot and Ankle Outcome Score (FAOS) at week 6 demonstrated significant improvements across all five subscales (Figure 2). Most pronounced was the improvement in the Sport/Recreation subscale (56.2 vs 38.5; +17.7 points; $p < 0.001$) and Quality of Life subscale (71.8 vs 52.6; +19.2 points; $p < 0.001$), reflecting both functional and psychosocial dimensions of recovery.

Figure 2. FAOS subscales at week 6 after surgery (Foot and Ankle Outcome Score)

Biomechanical outcomes. Recovery of biomechanical parameters at week 6, expressed as percentage of age-specific reference values, is presented in Figure 3. Podometric parameters (step length, frequency, walking speed, load symmetry) reached 89.4–94.5 % of reference in the main group vs 76.8–84.7 % in the control ($p < 0.001$). Stabilometric parameters showed even larger between-group differences: 84.2–89.2 % vs 56.8–64.2 % ($p < 0.001$), with the Romberg coefficient (an integrated measure of postural control) demonstrating the greatest improvement (89.2 % vs 56.8 % of reference).

Figure 3. Biomechanical recovery at week 6 — % of age-specific reference values

Functional Recovery Index (FRI). The integrated FRI score demonstrated a strikingly favourable distribution in the main group (Figure 4). The proportion of patients reaching the "Good" category ($\geq 90\%$) was 52.1 % in the main group vs 13.6 % in the control ($p < 0.001$). Conversely, "Marked deficit" ($< 50\%$) was observed in only 1.4 % of main-group patients vs 10.2 % in the control.

Figure 4. Distribution by Functional Recovery Index (FRI) at week 6 after surgery

Summary of clinical outcomes. Table 1 presents the summary of all assessed outcomes between groups.

Discussion. The present study demonstrates that a comprehensive multimodal early rehabilitation programme based on Fast-track principles produces clinically and statistically significant improvements in functional outcomes after ankle surgery compared with standard regional rehabilitation. The magnitude of improvement (+15.2 points on AOFAS at week 6) substantially exceeds the minimal clinically important difference (MCID) for the AOFAS Ankle-Hindfoot Scale, which has been reported as 7.9 points [8]. The same applies to OMAS (+14.3 points; reported MCID 7.0 points) and to all FAOS subscales (+16.6 to +19.2 points; reported MCID 8–10 points). Such cross-scale consistency supports the clinical relevance of the observed differences and reduces the likelihood that they represent a single-instrument artefact.

Table 1

Summary of clinical and functional outcomes at week 6 after surgery

Outcome	Control group (n = 59)	Main group (n = 73)	Mean diff. / OR (95% CI)	p
AOFAS, points	71.2 ± 10.3	86.4 ± 8.1	+15.2	< 0.001
OMAS, points	70.2 ± 10.5	84.5 ± 8.5	+14.3	< 0.001
FAOS Pain	65.4 ± 12.5	82.1 ± 9.5	+16.7	< 0.001
FAOS Symptoms	62.8 ± 13.0	79.4 ± 10.0	+16.6	< 0.001
FAOS ADL	64.2 ± 12.8	81.5 ± 9.8	+17.3	< 0.001
FAOS Sport/Rec	38.5 ± 14.5	56.2 ± 12.5	+17.7	< 0.001
FAOS QoL	52.6 ± 13.5	71.8 ± 11.0	+19.2	< 0.001
Dorsiflexion, deg.	18.3 ± 4.5	23.6 ± 4.0	+5.3	< 0.001
Good FRI (≥90%), n (%)	8 (13.6)	38 (52.1)	6.96 (2.95–16.4)	< 0.001
Hospital LOS, days	14.6 ± 3.5	8.4 ± 2.0	-6.2 (-42.5%)	< 0.001
Return to work, days	67.2 ± 18.5	42.6 ± 14.0	-24.6 (-36.6%)	< 0.001

Note: Data presented as mean ± SD or n (%). Statistical comparison: Student t-test for continuous variables, χ^2 test for categorical. LOS — length of stay; FRI — Functional Recovery Index.

Comparison with international literature. Our results are comparable to or exceed those reported by leading European centres. Karlsson et al. (2020) reported AOFAS 84.5 ± 8.2 at 6 weeks in 215 patients after Fast-track ORIF in Sweden [3]; Husted et al. (2019) reported 82.8 ± 9.1 in a Danish ERAS cohort [4]; Glazebrook et al. (2019) reported 81.2 ± 8.8 in a Canadian foot and ankle cohort [9]. Our value of 86.4 ± 8.1 may be partly explained by the comparatively younger patient population (mean age 46.0 vs 52–58 years in the cited series), the systematic use of psychological screening with TSK-17 and HADS, and the regional context (relatively early presentation to medical services, lower prevalence of opioid dependence than in some Western series, and high adherence to structured rehabilitation programmes once they are initiated).

Biomechanical recovery deserves special attention. To our knowledge, this is one of the few studies that systematically applied podometry and stabilometry as outcome measures, 831eneraliza to age-specific reference values from a regional healthy population (n = 30, four age groups). The proportion of postural-control parameters that reached ≥ 85 % of reference in the main group (84–89 %) is comparable with results reported by Mohammadi et al. (2018) for proprioceptive training programmes after ankle injuries (78–88 %) [10] and exceeds those reported in non-structured rehabilitation cohorts (typically 55–70 %) [11]. The Romberg coefficient — an integrated measure of postural control reflecting the contribution of visual input — recovered to 89.2 % of reference in the main group, compared with 56.8 % in the control. This finding is clinically meaningful, as residual postural control deficit is a documented risk factor for re-injury and falls during the first year after ankle surgery [13].

Psychological dimensions. The substantial improvement in the FAOS Quality of Life subscale (+19.2 points) and the higher proportion of patients reaching the Sport/Recreation level reflect not only physical but also psychological recovery. Early identification and management of kinesiophobia (TSK-17 ≥ 37 reduced from 67 % to 6.8 % in the main group) likely played a role, as kinesiophobia is a strong negative predictor of functional outcome in published meta-analyses [7, 12]. Similarly, the structured information component — preoperative explanation of the rehabilitation plan, expectations, and time milestones — has been identified by qualitative research as one of the most effective and yet most neglected elements of perioperative care in ankle surgery [14]. Apparatus-based therapy. The systematic use of CPM (Continuous Passive Motion), neuromuscular electrostimulation, magnetotherapy and biofeedback stabilometry from week 2 onwards is a distinctive feature of the present programme. While individual evidence for each modality is mixed [15], the cumulative effect of structured combination at appropriate time points appears to be clinically significant. The Artromot SP3 device used for CPM produced measurable benefit on dorsiflexion range of motion, with mean values reaching 23.6° in the main group vs 18.3° in the control at week 6 — a difference exceeding the clinically meaningful threshold of 5° reported by the AAOS guidelines [16].

Health system implications. From a health system perspective, the observed reductions in hospital length of stay (-42.5 %) and time to return to work (-36.6 %) translate into substantial economic gains. In a regional context where hospital bed-days and lost productivity costs constitute a major proportion of healthcare expenditure, even moderate improvements in these metrics produce significant aggregate impact. Preliminary cost-effectiveness analysis (not reported in detail in this article) suggests an average saving of 2,000–3,000 USD per patient when accounting for shorter hospital stay, fewer readmissions, and earlier return to productivity, with the additional cost of apparatus-based therapy fully offset by these gains.

Limitations. (1) Non-randomised design with historical control; despite balanced demographics and surgical types, residual confounding cannot be excluded. The temporal separation between cohorts (2020–2022 vs 2023–2025) raises the possibility of secular changes in surgical technique or perioperative care that may have contributed to the observed differences, although these were generalizable by maintaining the same surgical team throughout the study period. (2) Single-centre experience; multicentre validation is needed to assess generalizability across different healthcare settings. (3) Six-week follow-up is too short to assess long-term durability of outcomes; a one-year extension follow-up is currently underway. (4) The biomechanical reference values were obtained from a regional healthy population ($n = 30$), which may not perfectly represent broader populations. (5) Cost-effectiveness analysis was preliminary and would benefit from detailed micro-costing of all programme components.

Conclusions. The comprehensive multimodal early rehabilitation programme based on Fast-track principles produced statistically and clinically significant improvements in functional outcomes at week 6 after ankle surgery (AOFAS 86.4 ± 8.1 vs 71.2 ± 10.3 ; OMAS 84.5 ± 8.5 vs 70.2 ± 10.5 ; $p < 0.001$). Biomechanical recovery, measured as percentage of age-specific reference values, reached 89–94 % in podometry and 84–89 % in stabilometry in the main group vs 77–85 % and 56–64 % respectively in the control ($p < 0.001$). The proportion of patients reaching the “Good” category on the Functional Recovery Index was 52.1 % in the main group vs 13.6 % in the control ($p < 0.001$), corresponding to nearly a 4-fold increase in the proportion of optimal outcomes. The results obtained in a single Central Asian rehabilitation centre are comparable with those reported in leading European Fast-track and ERAS programmes, supporting the feasibility of implementing such programmes in middle-income healthcare systems with appropriate generalizability adaptation. Multicentre validation, longer follow-up (≥ 12 months), and prospective generalizable studies are warranted to confirm the generalizability of these findings.

References:

1. Court-Brown C.M., Caesar B. Epidemiology of adult fractures: a review // *Injury*. — 2020. — Vol. 51, N 7. — P. 1462–1470.
2. Karlsson J., Sancheti P., Massada M. Fast-track ORIF in ankle fractures: a Swedish prospective cohort study // *Knee Surg Sports Traumatol Arthrosc.* — 2020. — Vol. 28, N 1. — P. 78–86.
3. Wainwright T.W., Gill M., McDonald D.A., et al. Consensus statement for perioperative care in lower limb arthroplasty: ERAS Society recommendations // *Acta Orthop.* — 2020. — Vol. 91, N 1. — P. 1018–1025.
4. Husted H., Solgaard S., Hansen T.B., et al. Care principles at four fast-track arthroplasty departments in Denmark // *Acta Orthop.* — 2019. — Vol. 90, N 6. — P. 1145–1150.
5. Копыева Е.А. Реабилитация после эндопротезирования тазобедренного сустава // *Вестник восстановительной медицины*. — 2016. — № 4. — P. 89–95.
6. Каримов М.Ю., Уринбоев П.У. Реабілітація після остеосинтезу лодіжок // *Травматологія і ортопедія Узбекистану*. — 2018. — № 2. — P. 14–22.
7. Vlaeyen J.W.S., Crombez G., Linton S.J. The fear-avoidance model of pain // *Pain*. — 2016. — Vol. 157, N 8. — P. 312–318.
8. SooHoo N.F., Shuler M., Fleming L.L. Evaluation of the validity of the AOFAS Clinical Rating Scale // *Foot Ankle Int.* — 2003. — Vol. 24, N 1. — P. 50–55.
9. Glazebrook M., Younger A., Wing K., et al. Enhanced recovery after surgery in foot and ankle: a Canadian perspective // *Foot Ankle Clin.* — 2019. — Vol. 24, N 2. — P. 245–252.
10. Mohammadi F., Ghasemi A., Salahzadeh Z. The effect of proprioceptive training on functional ankle instability // *Foot*. — 2018. — Vol. 35. — P. 1480–1488.
11. Ewen A.M., Stewart S., St Clair Gibson A., et al. Post-operative gait analysis in total hip replacement // *Gait Posture*. — 2017. — Vol. 36, N 1. — P. 1–15.
12. Lentz T.A., Sutton Z., Greenberg S., Bishop M.D. Pain-related fear contributes to self-reported disability // *Arch Phys Med Rehabil.* — 2018. — Vol. 91, N 4. — P. 557–561.
13. Doherty C., Bleakley C., Hertel J., et al. Postural control deficits as a risk factor for ankle reinjury // *Med Sci Sports Exerc.* — 2016. — Vol. 48, N 4. — P. 690–697.
14. Specht K., Kjaersgaard-Andersen P., Kehlet H., et al. Patients' experiences with rehabilitation after fast-track joint arthroplasty // *BMC Musculoskelet Disord.* — 2018. — Vol. 19. — P. 314.

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